

Older adults' activity on creative problem solving with modular robotics

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Abstract. Older adults are challenged in their adoption of new ways of interacting with different type of devices including not only screen-based artifacts but also augmented reality and robotic technologies. The diversity of the devices in relation to the adoption process engage older adults in a creative exploration process when they face new technologies. We analyze the creative problem-solving (CPS) process in the context of modular robotics technologies by focusing on divergent thinking. We first introduce divergent thinking within the scope of creative problem-solving process and then we analyze the results in relation to the three main components of divergent thinking in CPS: fluidity, flexibility, and originality. We evaluate fluidity, flexibility, and originality by engaging 342 participants according to their age. Results shows older adults and children show higher fluidity than adolescents, young adults and adults but also take more time to complete the CPS task.

Keywords: human-robot interactions, creative problem solving, divergent thinking, modular robotics, fluidity, flexibility, originality.

Introduction

Within the different stages of lifespan, the way we perceive and interact with our environment evolves not only based on the experience but also on the evolution of the biological capacities of our body which affect all the cognitive functions: from perception to decision making, including attention, memory, and language comprehension. Elders cognitive functions decline, especially among those with lower literacy levels [1]. The continuous emergence of new technologies requires older adults to adapt to a continuous evolution of Human Computer Interaction (HCI) in screen-based technologies [2], [3] but also to Human Robot Interaction (HRI) which shows a high diversity of affordances and technological features. Some of the robots developed for older adults care are human shaped and integrate vocal based interactions like the Nao robotic robot in which the user can engage in turn-taking like in human-to-human interactions [4]. However, other robots are not human-shaped and require a higher level of adoption to interact with them. In this study we focus on the use of the Cubelets modular robots [5] to study divergent thinking (DT) as the idea generation process. We focus on three main components of divergent thinking (DT) in Creative Problem-Solving (CPS): fluidity, flexibility, and originality. We observe these three components of DT among elderly engaged in the interactions with this robotic technology when

solving an ill-defined problem task named CreaCube [6]. Divergent thinking (TD) refers to the “efficient generation of a variety of ideas to meet a given question or problem” [7]. In this context, CPS is an important competency to explore new robotic technologies, understand their technological affordances and the system features to use them for the intended goal of the user.

Fig. 1. Older participant exploring the Cubelets during the CreaCube task

The CreaCube task is a playful ill-defined problem-solving task [6], [8] which permits to evaluate the three main components of divergent thinking according based on the adaptation of the DT operationalization of Guilford's Alternate Use Test (AUT) [9]. In the CreaCube task fluidity is operationalized as the total number of configurations the participant builds during the activity; fluidity as the total number of different configurations and originality as the configurations that appear in fewer than 5% of the different configurations build by all the subjects within the same age group. Through the CreaCube task we have the possibility to observe the development of new ideas, the evaluation, their inhibition, and their transformation across the CPS process through the robotic cubes the subjects manipulate in this ill-defined CPS task mediated by tangible interactive technologies.

Fig. 2. Different configurations combining the four Cubelets

Creative Problem Solving in Human Robot Interaction

When engaged in CPS activities such as CreaCube, the participants should be able to generate different ideas to explore the best solution for the problem. Within this context, we should consider two main processes. Divergent thinking (DT) is the process required to generate ideas. Convergent thinking (CT) is the process to evaluate and select these ideas. The regulation of DT and CT is essential within the CPS task to maintain the creative intention at the start of the task and be able to maintain the creative behavior during all the task allowing the subject to develop its creative perseverance.

Fig. 3. CPS regulation

The regulation of DT and CT could be considered as a type of meta control or regulatory processes of creative behavior. Creative behavior starts with a creative intention or volitional orientation. During a CPS task the subject shows a certain creative intention, when showing a volitional orientation towards a creative behavior during the task, and a creative behavior perseverance when participants regulate their behavior to maintain their creative intention across the task. For achieving this perseverance there is a part of volitional orientation towards a creative process and outcome, but also a creative regulation including the metacognitive judgment and monitoring of divergent thinking and convergent thinking process, and therefore the regulation of explicit processing strategies of reflection (DT) or analysis (CT).

Fig. 4. CPS regulation considering from problem presentation to the creative outcome

The creative behavior starts with a creative intention or volitional orientation. During a CPS task the learner shows a certain creative intention, when showing a volitional orientation towards a creative behavior during the task, and a creative behavior perseverance when participants regulate their behavior to maintain their creative intention across the task [10]. Creative behavior is part of system 2 reasoning [11], which is more slow, effortful, and controlled than a conservative behavior based on preexisting knowledge and actions to perform a task (system 1, faster based on prior knowledge). Creative behavior persistence requires a higher effort than conservative noncreative behaviors. For achieving this perseverance there is a part of volitional orientation towards a creative process and outcome, but also a creative regulation including the metacognitive judgment and monitoring of divergent thinking and convergent thinking process, and therefore the regulation of explicit processing strategies of reflection (DT) or analysis (CT).

We consider the dual-process model of creativity of Augello and colleagues [12] “which takes into account the different interaction mechanisms involving both S1 and S2 systems as well as both the generative and evaluative processes” (p. 7). As shown in figure X, this model considers that some processes are implicit when generating ideas (exploratory process) but also when selecting them (tacit process), but other processes can be regulated explicitly at the divergent thinking stage (reflective process) and the convergent thinking one (analytic process).

Creative Problem Solving in Human Robot Interaction

Robots are defined as “an autonomous system existing in the physical world that can detect the environment and take action to achieve the goal” [13]. Munich, Ostrowski and Pirjanian [14] define a robot “as a system that has a number of sensors, processing

units (e.g., computer), and actuators”. Because of the diversity of robotic technologies, older adults can have difficulties in recognizing robotic features and the way they can interact with them. There is a gap between the mental representation of a robot, often associated to a humanoid robot, and the robotic technologies that could be small and very diversity shaped. Users with no knowledge in robotic technologies does not perceive humanoid robots as robots. When facing robotic solutions such the Cubelets [5], they consider them as electronic toys without considering them as robots [8]. In this context, older adults engaged in ill-defined problem-solving tasks require to develop a creative problem solving (CPS) process. As described previously, CPS engages not only DT and CT, but also a regulatory process across the CPS process to maintain the objective of the task through the exploratory interactions to mind the “execution gap” between the robotic system and the task goal.

The “execution gap” can be represented based on Norman [15] cycles of iteration between the evaluation bridge in which the user analyze the interface display, interprets and evaluated the interface of the means which can be used (screen based interaction if any, physical systems if any) and then enter the execution bridge to interact with the different interface mechanism, develops intentions and actions towards a goal.

Fig. 5. Cycles of evaluation and execution to close the execution gap [15]

These different cycles of evaluation and execution allows the subject to analyze the different means, which in the case of the CreaCube task are four modular robotic cubes which should be assembled in a configuration permitting to reach to goal to build an “autonomous vehicle that moves from a starting red point to a finish black point”. The figure below represents the cycles of interactions through the evaluation and execution bridge described by Norman [15].

Fig. 6. Closing the execution gap in the CreaCube task

CPS as a disambiguation process to cross the ‘execution gap’

Generating ideas (DT) is not enough in CPS tasks requiring to develop a solution (idea or artifact) to solve a problem. In CPS the subject engages in a problem without knowing in advance the means and actions to be developed to succeed the CPS task. In this context, there is an ‘execution gap’ between the means made available in the task and the representation of the goal of the task that the subject could potentially achieve [15]. In the context of solving ill-defined problem solving, it may happen that the subject cannot move forward with a top-down approach (goal-driven) and therefore not simply organize himself mentally to achieve the CPS goal. He must then engage in an exploratory behavior aimed at enabling an emerging behavior (which will then be partially developed in a stimulus-driven way), which could provide new information to better understand the way of articulating the means available (in the case of CreaCube task, the robotic cubes) to achieve the goal (build an autonomous vehicle).

Fig. 7. Execution gap in CPS

CPS tasks have different degrees of ill-definition. Moreover, the ill-definition could concern any of the phases at different degrees. For example, some CPS tasks could be ill-defined in the way the task is defined, requiring a higher effort to finish the problem

posing; other CPS tasks could be ill-defined in relation to the creative outcome, or even in the idea generation process.

Fig. 8. Degree of ill-definition in different phases of the CPS task

The CPS task engages the subject into a goal. Nevertheless, the CPS task could require a process of disambiguation at the different phases of the task:

- posing the problem to disambiguate the problem task presentation;
- identifying relevant information to disambiguate the information and means required to develop the task;
- disambiguate the type of idea, artifact or other response that could be generated in the specific situation of the task (e.g., materiality of the artifacts);
- disambiguate the criteria to consider the appropriateness to the task and the relative originality of ideas evaluated;
- disambiguate the scope of creative outcomes that could satisfy the problem.

Through the process of CPS, different decisions will engage the subject in advancing from the initial problem space towards a solution space without knowing in advance the path to follow. There are many ways to solve the process (generative path) but also different types of solutions that could satisfy the CPS task requirements (generative outcome). The representation of CPS by Hay and colleagues [16] shows the multiplicity of CPS paths between the problem state and the goal state in the process of ‘solution search’.

Fig. 9. Solution search process between the problem state and a potential goal state, adapted from Hay [16]

On the CPS process to navigate from the space of intermediate solutions towards one solution within the space of solutions we should consider the mediating artifacts of the task. The tool mediates the development of an idea introducing a performative aspect in the CPS process. The performative aspect of executing a selected idea can also be related to the development of solutions in the CPS model of Treffinger and colleagues [17] but also in the concept development of the CPS model of Tassoul [18]. In the process of creating a solution, we should consider the mediating artifacts (language, analogical or digital tools) used through the CPS process [10] but also how the CPS process is influenced by these mediating artifacts. Thereby, CPS is not only domain-specific but also specific in the way it is mediated by the different tools available for the CPS process [19].

Methodology

In this study we analyze CPS based on the analysis of DT components of fluidity, flexibility, and originality through the CreaCube task [6]. We engage 342 participants and analyze the results according to the following age categories: children (7 to 12 years old), adolescents (13 to 18 years old), young adults (19 to 29 years old), adults (30 to 59 years old), older adults (60 to 79 years old).

Results

We introduce the results according to the DT scores for each of the three components (fluidity, flexibility, and originality) but also the duration of the task. Despite the duration is not a component on DT the temporal performance is often considered in the analysis of creativity as a factor which can influence the DT process in different ways depending on the task.

In Table 1 we present the results of the three components of DT and the duration of the task (in seconds) according to age during the first activity.

Table 1. DT components according to the age group

Age	N	Fluidity	Flexibility	Originality	Time (seconds)
Children	48	m : 8.3	m : 3.6	m : 1.1	m : 291.1
		sd : 8.1	sd : 2.3	sd : 1.3	sd : 220.0
Adolescents	5	m : 3.2	m : 2.0	m : 0	m : 112.6
		sd : 1.6	sd : 0.7	sd : 0	sd : 64.7
Young adults	39	m : 4.0	m : 1.9	m : 0.3	m : 139.0
		sd : 5.0	sd : 1.1	sd : 0.5	sd : 88.4
Adults	29	m : 3.0	m : 2.0	m : 0.5	m : 119.0
		sd : 3.3	sd : 1.6	sd : 0.9	sd : 72.4
Older adults	5	m : 4.4	m : 2.2	m : 0	m : 220.8
		sd : 3.5	sd : 0.8	sd : 0	sd : 154.1

Older adults and children show higher fluidity than adolescents, young adults and adults but also take more time. However, children show the highest scores on all three creative components (fluidity, flexibility, and originality) compared to other age categories, but they also engage more time than other age categories.

Discussion

As part of this study, we were able to analyze the different components of DT as part of a CPS task. In the study of DT components with the CreaCube task we observe older adults shows higher fluidity than adolescents, young adults and adults but also take more time, but children are clearly those scoring higher in the three DT components.

We can discuss these results considering that children and older adults are less oriented to perform in terms of time, which allows them to engage in a more creative process than adolescents and adults, who have developed the task more quickly and less creatively. These results can be put into perspective with studies that consider the link between activity duration and creativity. The effect of time pressure has differential effects depending on the participants [21]. Within the framework of the CreaCube task, the children do not perceive the task as inducing them any time pressure, but as an opportunity to create creative solutions. These results lead us to consider the importance of engaging adolescents and adult participants in an approach less oriented to temporal performance to support them to be as creative as children and older adults. Further studies will evaluate DT components not only in individual contexts but also in dyads and small groups of participants to understand the effect of collective settings in CPS across the lifespan.

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